

ACTION OF NITROGEN DIOXIDE AND ITS DISSOCIATION PRODUCTS ON NITRITES OF SODIUM, POTASSIUM AND SILVER

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The action of nitrogen dioxide and its thermal dissociation products has been studied at about 130° and at temperatures above 130° for half an hour on AgNO₂, KNO₂ and NaNO₂. Only AgNO₂ reacts appreciably at 130°; the anhydrous nitrites, stable at 130°, are found not to react at this temperature. KNO₂ reacts at 140°, and NaNO₂ at 200°; the reaction is maximum at 200° in the case of KNO₂ and at 250° in the case of NaNO₂; in either case the reaction diminishes thereafter.

The action of nitrogen dioxide on silver nitrite was studied by Divers and Schimidzu (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1885, 47, 630) who found no action between the two. Ostwald (*Ann. chim.*, 1914, ix, 1, 44) found that nitrites underwent oxidation by nitrogen tetroxide and nitrogen dioxide below 100°, while Partington and Williams (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 947) found that above 180° nitrites became oxidised to nitrate. Addison and Lewis (*ibid.*, 1953, 1874) were of the opinion that nitrites underwent little change in contact with nitrogen tetroxide and its thermal dissociation products up to 130°.

The present work was planned to study the action of nitrogen dioxide and its thermal dissociation products formed above 130° on anhydrous nitrites. The results of the present work show that the reaction is dependent also on the nature of the nitrite.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium nitrite used was the pure salt, recrystallised and analysed for purity. Potassium nitrite was the same as that prepared by Oza and Walawalkar (*this Journal*, 1943, 20, 315). Silver nitrite was the same as used by Oza, Oza and Thaker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2457).

The experimental technique and apparatus were the same as described by Oza, Oza and Thaker (*loc. cit.*). The results recorded in Table I show that (i) in the case of NaNO₂ and KNO₂, the amount of N₂O₄ formed is very nearly equal to the amount of N₂O₄ consumed; (ii) except with AgNO₂, which begins to decompose at 128° (Oza, Oza and Thaker, *loc. cit.*), all the nitrite consumed is quantitatively oxidised to nitrate; (iii) with KNO₂ there is no reaction at 130°, but considerable one at 140°, while with NaNO₂ no reaction is observed even at 150°, and there is about 10% reaction at 200°; again, with KNO₂ the reaction is maximum at 200° and with NaNO₂ it is maximum at 250°, as above these temperatures the extent of the reaction is found to diminish; (iv) as distinguished from the behaviour of KNO₂ and NaNO₂, as pointed out under (i) and (ii), silver nitrite does not form its equivalent nitrate, evidently because a part of it decomposes: more nitric oxide ($\equiv$ of N₂O₄) is formed than expected if the behaviour were similar to KNO₂ and NaNO₂ while silver metal makes its appearance.

TABLE I

(a) System: $\text{NaNO}_3 + \text{NO}_2$										
Expt. No.	Temp.	Substance taken. (g.)	N_2O_4 taken. (g.)	Substance consumed. (g.)	Nitrate formed. (g.)	Metal formed. (g.)	Na_2O_4 left. (c.c.)	N_2O_4 consumed. (c.c.)	N_2O_3 formed. (c.c.)	Approx ratios. 5:9. 5:6. 5:10. 9:10.
1.	150°	0.2220	0.1710	...	...	...	41.5	...	...	...
2.	200°	0.2270	0.2355 (57.34)	0.0230 (3.35×10^{-4})	0.02845 (3.35×10^{-4})	...	51.2	6.14 (2.77×10^{-4})	6.2 (2.77×10^{-4})	I I I I I
3.	250°	0.1044	0.2250 (54.9)	0.07196 (10.4×10^{-4})	0.8860 (10.4×10^{-4})	...	32.3	22.6 (10.01×10^{-4})	22.4 (10.0×10^{-4})	I I I I I
4.	300°	0.1204	0.2850 (69.4)	0.0615 (8.9×10^{-4})	0.0758 (8.9×10^{-4})	...	49.2	22.5 (9.0×10^{-4})	22.0 (8.99×10^{-4})	I I I I I
5.	350°	0.1000	0.2240 (54.5)	0.0457 (6.0×10^{-4})	0.0563 (6.0×10^{-4})	...	39.7	14.8 (6.6×10^{-4})	14.9 (6.67×10^{-4})	I I I I I
(b) System: $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{NO}_2$										
6.	130°	0.1001	0.2754	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
7.	140°	0.1032	0.2810 (68.3)	0.05844 (6.87×10^{-4})	0.06944 (6.87×10^{-4})	...	52.9	15.4 (6.87×10^{-4})	15.62 (6.97×10^{-4})	I I I I I
8.	200°	0.1040	0.2110 (51.37)	0.0800 (9.41×10^{-4})	0.0050 (9.41×10^{-4})	...	30.37	21.0 (9.37×10^{-4})	21.2 (9.4×10^{-4})	I I I I I
9.	250°	0.1010	0.2374 (57.85)	0.06956 (8.18×10^{-4})	0.08256 (8.17×10^{-4})	...	39.65	18.2 (8.1×10^{-4})	18.5 (8.2×10^{-4})	I I I I I
10.	300°	0.1020	0.2390 (58.2)	0.06374 (7.5×10^{-4})	0.07574 (7.5×10^{-4})	...	41.8	16.4 (7.32×10^{-4})	16.6 (7.4×10^{-4})	I I I I I
11.	350°	0.1018	0.2194 (53.4)	0.05312 (6.25×10^{-4})	0.06312 (6.25×10^{-4})	...	39.4	14.0 (6.23×10^{-4})	14.2 (6.345×10^{-4})	I I I I I
* (c) System: $\text{AgNO}_3 + \text{NO}_2$										
12.	130°	0.2660	0.148 (36.04)	0.0405 (2.63×10^{-4})	0.0326 (2.13×10^{-4})	0.0043 (0.4×10^{-4})	27.8	8.24 (3.67×10^{-4})	8.82 (3.69×10^{-4})	0.72 I.2 0.67 0.94
13.	200°	0.2060	0.2650 (64.5)	0.1449 (9.4×10^{-4})	0.0916 (5.5×10^{-4})	0.04234 (3.9×10^{-4})	56.88	7.62 (3.4×10^{-4})	12.00 (5.3×10^{-4})	I.2 1.7 1.8 0.64

* These results are reproduced from Oza, Oza and Thaker (*loc. cit.*).

DISCUSSION

From these results it appears possible to infer that some anhydrous nitrites can react with nitrogen dioxide round about 130° . The temperature of the bath may be the temperature of the nitrite, but will not be the temperature of the gas, as a part of the system outside the bath is exposed to air. The overall temperature of the gas will therefore be less than those recorded in the table. At 140° , the molecular species of the nitrogen oxide is almost all NO_2 (Richardson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, 81, 397) and this temperature is probably slightly higher (Addison and Lewis, *loc. cit.*). Hence, it appears that the nitrites might undergo oxidation at $130\text{--}140^{\circ}$ as

forming nitrate and nitric oxide, as found in these experiments in the case of silver nitrite. This oxidation is found to occur not uniformly at $130\text{--}40^{\circ}$, and is therefore dependent on the nature of the nitrite.

Silver nitrite is oxidised at 130° . Although this substance is now known to commence decomposing at 128° , forming silver oxide, nitric oxide and nitrogen dioxide, and silver oxide to react with nitrogen dioxide (cf. Oza, Oza and Thaker, *loc. cit.*) as

the experimental results show unmistakably that this contributes but very little to the formation of nitrate found at 130° ; for Ag found and nitric oxide found in excess of the requirement of (i), are not very large at this temperature. At higher temperatures, these influences do play a part in the case of silver nitrite as there is no other way of explaining the large amount of nitric oxide formed, since Ag_2O reacts with NO_2 without forming nitric oxide (Oza, Oza and Thaker, *loc. cit.*): Silver is actually large at 200° .

In the case of sodium and potassium nitrites, the reaction (i) is found to occur at temperatures higher than 130° ; further, the temperature is higher with sodium nitrite than with potassium nitrite. As a matter of fact, potassium nitrite fuses and decomposes at a higher temperature than sodium nitrite does (Oza, this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 173). This shows that the reaction of nitrogen dioxide, forming nitrites, is not dependent on the prior decomposition of nitrite—an inference not unlikely from the behaviour of silver nitrite.

The only remaining observation of this work is the inversion in the course of oxidation of nitrite which occurs after a certain temperature with sodium and potassium nitrites. This must be ascribed to the effect of nitric oxide, increasingly formed, with rise of temperature, from NO_2 (as $\text{NO}_2 \longrightarrow \text{NO} + \frac{1}{2} \text{O}_2$) and also as in (i) above, on nitrate as

The reaction (ii) becomes prominent with rise in temperature (Oza, Oza and Thaker, *loc. cit.*).

The present work shows that nitrate found in the oxidation products of nitrite by nitrogen dioxide is the result of the reversible reaction (Oza and Oza, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 907 ; Oza, Oza and Thaker, *loc. cit.*) :

If the nitrite is not stable at the temperature of the experiment, some of it may also be formed as :

Above 130-40°, NO_2 is known to dissociate as $\text{NO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NO} + \frac{1}{2} \text{O}_2$ (Bodenstein and Kotayama, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1909, 18, 244), and it appears that the oxygen, so formed, may have but little effect in bringing about oxidation of the nitrite. The work of Johnston and Walker (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 172) shows that the concentration of atomic oxygen at such a temperature will be exceedingly small and negligible.

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